

Oslo, 09 July, 2025

Dear Dr Olwenn Martin,

Thank you for giving us the opportunity to submit a revised draft of the manuscript "Identification of concepts of importance for the assessment of internal validity of in vitro toxicology studies using a modified Delphi technique".

We appreciate the time and effort that you and the reviewers have dedicated to providing your valuable feedback and are grateful for the comments and suggestions for improvement of our manuscript. We have comprehensively revised our manuscript in accordance with the comments and suggestions. We have also responded to each comment individually, and the suggested revisions are shown in the table below. The table contain an overview of our point-by-point response to all comments and the revisions provided.

We look forward to hearing from you regarding our submission and to respond to any further questions and comments you may have.

Sincerely,

Gro Haarklou Mathisen

Responses to reviewer comments

TEBT-2025-0001

Comment-by-comment responses

Reviewer comment		Response
1.	<p>This paper documents a transparent, and high-quality process to determine the importance of items in the INVITES-IN study bank using a Delphi approach. However, as the authors note, this did not reduce the item bank considerably. From this work, it is clear that there are many experimental design and other considerations which may influence the internal validity of an in vitro toxicology study, with further work planned to turn this into a draft assessment tool. A key learning from this work is the complexity involved in arriving at a core list of important items. The authors discuss the advantages of a workshop-based approach (with more discussion and interaction about each item) over an out-of-context list presented during a Delphi survey.</p>	
2.	<p>The manuscript presents a potentially valuable contribution to the literature; however, substantial revisions are required before it can be accepted for publication. The manuscript has potential and could offer meaningful insights, but significant revisions are necessary. Clarifying the methodology, providing rationale for expert selection, improving</p>	<p>Thank you for suggesting improvements of the manuscript. The manuscript has been revised as suggested: the methodology is clarified, the rationale for the expert selection is included, the language is improved, and the referencing issues are corrected.</p>

	language precision, and correcting referencing issues will substantially enhance the quality of the work.	
3.	The context and rationale for this second study in the development of the INVITES-IN tool are described in sufficient detail. The objectives of both the development of the tool and this specific study are exposed	Thank you for the kind words.
4.	Some very minor comments on the description of the methods to avoid any ambiguity were spotted. Both can be addressed after peer-review. Regarding the eligibility criteria for participants, please clarify whether all criteria need to be met (i.e. both experience of in vitro methods and systematic review). Also, could you clarify what is meant by "Participants were able to return to the survey as many times as needed until the closure of the round."?	<p>Regarding the eligibility criteria for participants, we aimed to include participants with experience both with systematic review and in vitro methods.</p> <p>The Welphi software used allowed participants to work with the Delphi survey over time. Participants did not need to complete the survey before they logged out. Rather, the participants could log in and continue filling in the survey at another time. This is what was meant by: "Participants were able to return to the survey as many times as needed until the closure of the round". Since the survey was long (included 406 bias items), it was considered to be important that the survey could be completed over time.</p> <p>The following revision is included for clarification:</p>

		Section 2.4:“The Welphi software allowed the participants to log in and work with the survey as many times as needed until the closure of the round.”
5.	The methods were previously published, and authors have clearly referenced the pre-registered methods as well as described and justified any deviations from these. Detailed and complete supplementary information is made available allowing complete transparency of the process.	
6.	I am unfamiliar with ethical approval requirements in Norway, as I expect at least part of our readership would be. In other contexts, ethical approval for studies involving human participants is not restricted to studies that collect information on health, but is extended to other type of personal or sensitive information. It would be useful if you gave a bit more context to help us understand why ethical approval was not required.	<p>A Data Protection Impact Assessment was performed and approved by the Norwegian Institute of Public Health. Ethics approval was waived as no sensitive information was being collected.</p> <p>The text is revised as follows:</p> <p>“Ethics approval was waived as no sensitive information was being collected.”</p>
7.	Clarity on Methodological Approach and Design: There is considerable confusion regarding the methodological design, specifically the use of terms such as “Delphi Panel Guided discussions,” “focus group discussions,” and “workshops.” These are used interchangeably	“Focus group discussions” is used to describe the discussions that took place in the focus groups in Study One (creation of the item bank). The text has been revised throughout the manuscript to

<p>throughout the manuscript, which makes it difficult to ascertain the exact nature of the process undertaken. The authors must clarify whether the online engagement constituted a Delphi process, a focus group, or a workshop. It may be that the terminology overlaps because the authors refer to Delphi Panel Discussions as workshops while also describing focus group discussions in parallel. A clear distinction between these methodological components is essential for reader comprehension and for methodological rigor. The authors also used an explanatory sequential mixed methods design (quantitative survey followed by a Guided Delphi panel discussion) – perhaps this should be explicitly stated in the manuscript.</p>	<p>clarify that “focus group discussions” took place in Study One as follows: “focus group discussions in Study One”.</p> <p>Following the two-round Delphi survey, three Delphi Panel Guided discussions were arranged (the term “workshop” was used in the protocol). To clarify, the term “workshop” has been replaced by “guided Delphi panel discussion” throughout the manuscript.</p> <p>The overview of the methodology has been revised as follows:</p> <p>Section 2.1: The study included a two-round quantitative digital Delphi survey followed by online Delphi panel discussion guided by a moderator from the project team (referred to as a “workshop” in the protocol). The guided Delphi panel were used to discuss and obtain agreement on items that did not achieve agreement in the two-round Delphi survey. Each item was discussed in one guided Delphi panel, and participants were invited to one guided Delphi panel each. Three guided Delphi panels were</p>
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		arranged in total to enable smaller-group discussions on the items to make it possible to involve all participants in the discussions.
8.	Pilot testing of a survey should be done with a sample representative of the population for whom the survey was designed for (Line 193-194) – the authors would need to justify why they used a sample from their research team for this.	<p>Ideally, pilot testing would have been conducted with a sample of the population for whom the survey was designed. We did not have access to such a sample so instead piloted with project team members.</p> <p>The following explanation has been included in the manuscript:</p> <p>Section 2.3: Pilot testing of the survey was performed by a minimum of four persons in the research team before the start of both rounds. Ideally, pilot testing would have been conducted with a sample of the population for whom the survey was designed. Due to limited access to the intended sample, we opted to conduct the pilot with members of the project team.</p>
9.	Rationale for Panel Composition: The manuscript states that the Delphi Panel Review was conducted to reduce and refine a pool of items to achieve content validity. However, it is unclear why participants were required to have experience in systematic reviews, given that the	Experience with the assessment of internal validity was considered important for the identification of items of importance for the assessment of internal validity since the systematic review community has

	<p>process primarily concerns item selection and refinement. This requirement should be explained more explicitly. Additionally, the authors should address why experts with experience in item development were not included, as their input would be highly relevant to the task of item refinement.</p>	<p>longer experience in the assessment of internal validity and factors that may introduce bias compared to the chemical risk assessment community. This way, we aim to build on existing expertise and experience.</p> <p>The goal of our study was to identify items important for the assessment of internal validity of in vitro studies. Including sufficient participants with both systematic review and in vitro experience was therefore considered critical. Expertise with item development was not considered to be of the same importance, as item development was not the objective of this study.</p>
10.	<p>Yes, this adheres well to the pre-specified protocol with only small deviations. Most deviations are well explained in the manuscript. One element which should be added to the manuscript (or explained as an omission) is the inclusion of summary statistics for the ratings for each item. From protocol: “The average group response, changes in rating between rounds, as well as modifications of the questionnaire, will be reported. The expert panellists rating of the questions will be analysed independently for round 1, round 2, and the guided discussion, and</p>	<p>Supplementary materials 3 has been revised, and the average group response is included for both Delphi rounds. The following has been included in the manuscript in the “Deviation from the protocol” section:</p> <p>Section 2.6: “The average group response and the distribution of the participant ratings of each item are presented in Supplementary materials 3. The median, standard deviation and the interquartile</p>

	median, mean, standard deviation and the interquartile range will be reported.”	range are not reported, because the distribution of the participant ratings was considered more informative to detect potential “false agreement”.
11.	I was unclear on how, practically, the 166 items were discussed in the workshops, but the transcripts made this clear. It should be noted in the text that all items were discussed, but that each workshop looked at different bias domains to cover everything.	Each of the 166 items was discussed in one workshop. After three workshops, all 166 items were discussed. The manuscript is revised as follows for clarification: Section 2.5: “The items were grouped under bias domains, and the guided Delphi panel were structured so each domain was fully discussed. This allowed discussion of all items with ambiguous agreement.”
12.	Were the participants of study 1 (generating the item bank) and this study overlapping? This should be clear as if some participants originally suggested the items, they will be more likely to see them as important versus an independent group.	The participants in study 1 and the present Delphi study were not overlapping. This is now described in the manuscript: Section 2.2: “Participants in the focus group discussions in study 1 were not eligible for participation in the Delphi study.”
13.	I found some of the items difficult to disambiguate – for example “Blinded study” and “blinding of experiment”, “blinding”. Also, “randomisation methods”, “Choice of randomisation method”,	Participants were presented with decontextualized items and asked to rate if an item should be

	<p>randomisation of teeth”, “randomisation of samples” etc. In your lessons learned section, it may be worth reflecting on the similarity across some items and that this may have made it challenging to reduce the set substantially. Other items are hard to understand without further detail. I wasn’t completely sure whether there was any additional details provided for each or whether participants were given the list as is</p>	<p>considered when assessing the potential for bias in an in vitro study.</p> <p>We agree that some items are functionally equivalent (e.g. 105 “storage of test compound” and 2097 “storage of test materials”), as described in the item bank manuscript (Vist et al., 2024). The reason for keeping both is that we considered it important to preserve even small conceptual differences, not knowing if these may be significant to the development of an INVITES-IN appraisal tool in a way we cannot anticipate during the item identification process. Therefore, items included in the bank may still be equivalent, however, these were not removed in the deduplication process because we aimed to preserve even small nuanced conceptual differences.</p> <p>We agree that both the similarity across some items, and that some items were confusing to participants, may have affected the elimination of items. The following revisions is done in the discussion section for clarification:</p>
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		<p>Section 4.4: “Also, the similarity across some items may have been challenging for the participants.”</p>
<p>14.</p>	<p>It seems that items were only excluded as part of the guided discussion workshop phase. Can you add more detail on how exclusion decisions were determined in the workshops? The intended methodology for this isn't clear to me from the protocol / methods.</p>	<p>Items could be excluded at survey phase, it just turned out that this rarely happened.</p> <p>The workshop discussions were facilitated toward the goal of including or excluding items for which the survey responses were ambiguous. Based on the issues and arguments raised in the discussion with the workshop participants, the two investigators decided whether the item in question should be included or excluded.</p> <p>This was a subjective decision made by the team when we were confident that agreement had truly been reached through the discussion. The following is included for clarification:</p> <p>Section 2.5: “Based on the issues and arguments raised in the discussion with the Delphi panel participants, the two investigators decided whether the item in question should be included or excluded.”</p>

15.	<p>Another minor issue is related to the generation of the Sankey diagram (figure 2), the specific package and code are given but I could not find any mention of the R language environment and software version. On the same figure, it is unclear what happened to the 'Timing of study termination bias' items.</p>	<p>The R language environment and software version are now included:</p> <p>Section 3.2: “The Sankey Plot was generated using R packages: openxlsx (Schauberger and Walker, 2025), ggplot2 (Wickham, 2016), tidyverse (Wickham et al., 2019), and a ggsanky package (Sjoberg, 2024), which required installation of the devtools package (Wickham et al., 2022).”</p> <p>The Sankey plot has been replaced by a version with other colors, where the 'Timing of study termination bias' items are visible.</p>
16.	<p>I should flag that not all affiliations are given for all co-authors on Zenodo; there are only 15 institutions listed on Zenodo, whereas 29 are listed on the pre-print file.</p>	<p>All affiliations are listed in the manuscript. When the manuscript was uploaded on Zenodo, it was only possible to include one affiliation per co-author.</p>
17.	<p>Most co-authors have provided an informative up-to-date declaration of interests. There are a few declarations where the table part with check boxes does not match the narrative detailed explanation parts, others that are only signed with no information about interests or indication whether this specific author has no interests to declare or declined to complete the form. The dates of some declarations (about 2 years old)</p>	<p>When the study protocol was published, declarations of interest for several of the co-authors of this study were published. All co-authors have been given the possibility to update their declaration of interest. Unless there was a change in their interests that should be reported,</p>

	<p>suggest that these declarations may not be up-to-date. As these declarations are a public-facing record of authors' declarations, it would be appropriate to give these co-authors an opportunity to correct and/or to update their declarations.</p>	<p>the declarations of interest forms completed for the study protocol are the ones available on the Zenodo for this study.</p> <p>Declarations of interest from co-authors not co-authoring the protocol, e.g. Miles Davenport, is of a never date.</p>
18.	<p>Terminology and Language Use: The manuscript contains several inconsistencies and imprecise uses of language. For example, acronyms should be written out in full the first time they are used (see Page 4, Lines 104–105). Additionally, the phrase "obviously authoritative tool" (Line 110) should be revised for tone and precision - "existing comprehensive tool" may be a more appropriate alternative.</p>	<p>Thank you for this comment. The following revisions have been made:</p> <p>All acronyms are written out the first time they are used and explained in figure and table legends. Section 1: obviously authoritative tool is stated as "no obviously authoritative (i.e. generally accepted as valid)" to make our meaning clearer.</p>
19.	<p>Referencing Style: In-text citations require careful review to align with academic standards. For instance, on Line 119, the referencing format is inconsistent: "... described in Mathisen et al. (2023) and Svendsen et al (2023)."; Line 132 – 133: The use of semi-colons between references and the use of acronyms (EPA, 2022) and (NTP OHAT, 2015) - Ensure consistency with the chosen citation style throughout manuscript, including proper punctuation and writing out acronyms in full on first time use.</p>	<p>Thank you for this comment. All references are now according to the "Amer Assoc Agronomy" EndNote output style.</p>

<p>20.</p>	<p>Language and Editing: The manuscript would benefit from professional language editing. Several grammatical and stylistic issues hinder the clarity and flow of the text. A comprehensive proofreading and copy-editing process is strongly recommended prior to resubmission.</p> <p>Line 121-122 – “Study 1: Creation of a ... studies of any (Vist et al., 2024): Sentence incomplete”.</p> <p>Paragraph 2 Lines 284-291 – This paragraph is unclear and confusing – rephrase.</p> <p>Line 297 and 308 – Table 2 – Do you mean Figure 2?</p> <p>Discussion: It would help the reader if the author/s provide an outline of the findings to guide the reader at the outset.</p> <p>Page 19, Paragraph 3 – “As we discussed... desirable”. Sentence incomplete</p>	<p>Thank you for suggesting improvements of the language. Several revisions have been done to improve the language throughout the manuscript.</p> <p>The examples mentioned are included below.</p> <p>The text in line 121-122 is revised as follows:</p> <p>Section 1: “Study 1: Creation of a comprehensive database (“item bank”) of concepts that may be relevant for the assessment of internal validity of <i>in vitro</i> toxicity testing studies, completed in 2023 (Vist et al., 2024).”</p> <p>The text in paragraph 2 lines 284-291 is revised as follows:</p> <p>Section 3.2: “In the first Delphi round, the survey included 406 items. The participants agreed that 168 of the items should be considered when assessing potential for bias in an <i>in vitro</i> study. No new items were suggested by the participants, and none of the existing items were revised. The 238 items for which no consensus was reached in round 1, were included in the second round of the Delphi survey. In this round, the participants</p>
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		<p>agreed that 72 of the items should be considered when assessing potential for bias in an in vitro study. No items were excluded. The 166 items for which no agreement was identified were discussed in the online workshops. Based on these discussions, participants agreed that 33 of these items should not be considered when assessing potential for bias in an in vitro study. The dataset that will be the starting point for the creation of INVITES-IN therefore contains 373 bias items.”</p> <p>Section 3.2: we mean Table 2, not Figure 2. The following revision is made for clarification: “In addition to the overview presented in Figure 2, the number of items from each bias domain and each source included in the Delphi study, and the number of items per bias domain and source the participants agreed that should be/not should be considered when assessing potential for bias in an in vitro study, are shown in Tables 2 and 3 respectively.”</p>
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